

COMPARISON OF OVARIAN VOLUME IN FERTILE AND INFERTILE MARRIED FEMALES

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Abstract

Background: Infertility is a significant complication that affects women worldwide. It is certainly difficult to handle with this situation. Primary goal of this study is to measure the trans-abdominal ovarian volume in married, fertile, and infertile women.

Objective: To compare ovarian volume between fertile and infertile married female.

Methodology: 60 of the 120 participants in this cross-sectional study were fertile, while the remaining 60 were infertile. The study was carried out at Ali Fatima Hospital using a Toshiba XARIO XG machine with a convex probe operating at a frequency of 3-5 MHz. Only married women 18-40 year were included in the study; those with a history of hormone treatment, gynecological issues, or contraceptive pill use were excluded. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 25.

Results: In fertile patients, the mean ovarian volume of the right ovary was found to be 11.38, and the mean ovarian volume of the left ovary was 11.34. In infertile patients, the estimated mean ovarian volume of the right ovary was 5.81, and the estimated mean ovarian volume of the left ovary was 5.9776. The ovarian volumes of infertile patients were slightly lower than those of fertile patients. The results indicate a significant difference in the estimated ovarian volume between fertile and infertile individuals.

Conclusion: The study confirmed that the ovarian volume in infertile women is lower than in fertile women.

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is a worldwide health complication affecting roughly 8-10% in couples.¹ It is a multidimensional complication with social, economic and cultural implications.² Infertility is elucidated by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the incapability to conceive after 1 year of

unprotected intercourse for women under 35.³ In worldwide, a lower prevalence 10.4% of infertility is recorded in a community-based setting and a higher prevalence 79.3% is perceived in a hospital-based setting. The overall pooled prevalence of infertility is 46.25%⁴. A slight divergence in the

prevalence of infertility was observed. It is classified as primary or secondary. Primary infertility is denoted for those women who have not conceived previously. In secondary infertility, there is at least one conception, but it fails to repeat.⁵ It affects 10%-15% of couples in their lifetime.⁶ The prevalence of primary infertility is at 3.5% and secondary infertility is at 18.4%.⁷

There are many factors that can lead to infertility, they may include obesity, hypothyroidism, aging, polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) and hormonal imbalances.⁸ It is characterized by hormonal imbalances, metabolic disturbances, and reproductive abnormalities, leading to symptoms such as irregular menstrual cycles, ovarian cysts, hyperandrogenism, and insulin resistance.⁹ Aging is associated with a natural decline in female fertility due to changes in ovarian reserve, hormonal shifts, and alterations in egg quality.¹⁰ Obesity has major adverse effects on reproductive performance and fertility potential especially in women with polycystic ovary syndrome.¹¹ Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), characterized by multiple small cysts and hormonal imbalances, represents a multifaceted disorder with implications

METHODOLOGY:

It was a comparative study. The data was collected from Meer Khan Children and Family Hospital Lahore. The duration of the study spread to 7 months. Within a period of 7 months, all patients visiting the ultrasound clinic for gynecological ultrasound were included. Convenient sampling techniques were employed. The study included all fertile and infertile married women between 18 and 45 years of age. Women with gynecological abnormalities, on contraceptive medicine, and those under hormonal treatment were excluded from the study. Ultrasound

beyond reproductive health.¹² Endometriosis, which involves the presence of endometrial tissue outside the uterus affecting ovaries, Fallopian tubes and pelvic tissues which persists with significant implications.¹³ This is necessary to detect immunological and hormonal complications contributing to the formation and progress of endometriotic lesions to develop effective treatment strategies.¹⁴ Premature ovarian insufficiency (POI), which is defined by the initial termination of ovarian function before the age of 40 due to low estrogen level, irregular or absent menstrual cycle and often infertility.¹⁵

The ovarian volume generally decreases with increasing female age.¹⁶ Ovarian volume is greatest in the 18-26 age range, and there is a strong relationship between ovarian volume and fertility. The fertile population has larger ovarian volumes compared to the infertile population.¹⁷ Postmenopausal women's ovarian volumes were smaller than those of premenopausal women of the same age.¹⁸

Ovarian volume can be measured with ultrasound to evaluate infertility which is not only less expensive than measuring hormone levels but also non-invasive.

machines used were Toshiba Xario and Minder DP7. The consent informed from all the participants was safe, ensuring their oblivion and privacy throughout the research. The data was collected using the data sheet which were based on operating definitions. Patients were instructed to hydrate at least 24 ounces of water one hour before the test to fill the bladder adequately, allowing a clear view of the ovary. The patient was deployed Supine. The ovaries are located on either side of the uterus and can be identified by scanning the lateral or longitudinal planes adjacent to the uterine body.

RESULTS:

Fertility status					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Fertile	60	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Infertile	60	50.0	50.0	100.0
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	

Total sample size is 120. No. of fertile women are 60 and infertile are 60. Infertility classified into primary and secondary infertility .No. Of primary infertility is 28 has 23.3% whereas no. secondary infertility is 32 has 26.7%.

Type of infertilities					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Normal	60	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Primary infertility	28	23.3	23.3	73.3
	Secondary infertility	32	26.7	26.7	100.0
	Total	120	100.0	100.0	

ANOVA Table							
				Mean			
Group Statistics							
Ovarian volume - Right	Betw	Fertility status	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P-value
Ovarian volume - Right	Within Groups			1931.132	119	6.437	
	Total			1931.132	119	6.437	
	Between Groups (Combined)			974.654	15	64.977	10.094
Ovarian volume - Left	Within Groups			669.461	104	6.437	
	Total			1644.115	119	6.437	
	Between Groups (Combined)			974.654	15	64.977	10.094

ANOVA Table								
				Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Ovarian volume - Right	Between Groups (Combined)			1054.423	15	70.295	8.339	.000
	Within Groups			876.709	104	8.430		
	Total			1931.132	119			
Ovarian volume - Left	Between Groups (Combined)			974.654	15	64.977	10.094	.000
	Within Groups			669.461	104	6.437		
	Total			1644.115	119			

Ovarian volume - Right ovary	Fertile	60	11.3078	3.25924	.42077	.000
	Infertile	60	5.6408	2.40391	.31034	
Ovarian volume - Left ovary	Fertile	60	11.2767	2.72782	.35216	.000
	Infertile	60	5.7887	2.26076	.29186	

Among fertile, The right ovary's mean ovarian volume was found to be 11.3078 with a standard deviation of 3.25925, The left ovary's mean ovarian volume was found to be 11.2767 with The right ovary's mean ovarian volume was a standard deviation of 2.72782 based on data from 60 individuals. In the infertile, the slightly lower 5.6408, with a standard deviation of 2.40391, And the left ovary's mean ovarian volume was found to be 5.7887 with a standard deviation of 2.26076 involving 60 participants. Results are significantly correlated to each other.

The length of infertility and ovarian volume for both ovaries were found to be statistically significantly correlated by a one-way ANOVA ($p < .001$). Compared to the left ovary ($F = 10.094$, $MS = 64.977$), the right ovary displayed more variance ($F = 8.339$, $MS = 70.295$). According to these results, ovarian morphology may be impacted by prolonged infertility, which calls for more research into the potential clinical ramifications. The study found a significant correlation between the length of marriage and ovarian volume changes in both right and left ovaries, $F(26,93) = 2.084$, $p = .006$ for the right ovary, Left Ovarian: $p = .012$, $F(26,93) = 1.927$ suggesting age-related physiological changes or lifestyle modifications, and suggesting time-dependent reproductive trends by ANOVA analysis. For both ovaries, statistical analysis revealed a highly significant variation in ovarian volume among the various kinds of infertility: $F(2,117) = 58.431$, $p < .001$, right ovary, $F(2,117) = 71.461$, $p < .001$, left ovary, According to these findings, ovarian volume varies significantly based on the type of infertility, which may indicate that different pathophysiological mechanisms underlie each type by using ANOVA analysis.

DISCUSSION:

The research covered 120 individuals, who have been evenly cut up into fertile ($n = 60$) and infertile groups ($n = 60$), classified into primary (23.3%) and secondary infertility (26.7%). This thorough analysis encompasses the complete spectrum of infertility instances, representing the complete sample.

According to the study, secondary infertility is marginally more common than primary infertility in the population (26.7% vs. 23.3%), which could be caused by regional or epidemiological trends. The average age is between 1 and 18 years old, and the average marriage lasts 9.02 years. The average duration for infertile participants is 3.40 years. The mean ovarian volume on the right ovary was $8.47 \pm 4.03 \text{ cm}^3$, and on the left ovary was $8.53 \pm 3.72 \text{ cm}^3$. Whereas according to a study of Yang et Al the average ovarian volume in a Chinese population was determined by studying a fertile woman to be 3.90 cm^3 . demonstrates that ovarian volume varies by area and is clearly influenced by demographic variables. Yang et Al, (2022).¹⁹

Group statistics reveal a clear difference in ovarian volume between fertile and infertile women as right ovarian volume in fertile women is $11.31 \pm 3.26 \text{ cm}^3$ and Infertile women is $5.64 \pm 2.40 \text{ cm}^3$. Meanwhile left ovarian volume in fertile women is $11.28 \pm 2.73 \text{ cm}^3$ and Infertile women is $5.79 \pm 2.26 \text{ cm}^3$. This indicates that both right and left ovarian volumes were substantially larger in fertile women compared to infertile women, with relatively small standard errors (right ovary SE: 0.42 vs. 0.31; left ovary. Whereas according to Nelson study ageing have major effect on ovarian volume as we can see with advancing age especially before menopause ovarian volume decreases as compare to youngsters. Study found that

the mean ovarian volume in a study done in Egypt was 9.9 cm³, which is comparable to our value. Nelson (2013) at el.²⁰

A downward trend in the ovarian volume is demonstrate the ovarian ageing, which is previously perceived than an increase in FSH concentration and is fine prognosticator of poor response to ovulation induction. ARYA et al (2023).²¹ According to Qiao, J. et al. (2022) recent study found a correlation between women's infertility during their late reproductive years and the reduced OR indicated by low AMH. It has been found that as people age, their OR decreases, which results in infertility.²² Expansion of the uterine corridor blood stream blockage has been linked to infertility that cannot be explained, according to Steer et al. (2017).²³ In a study Erdem et al in 2003y , their data suggested that for women over 35 who are having trouble conceiving, it might be better to use TVU (transvaginal ultrasound) instead of hormonal tests. TVU can give us a better idea of ovarian reserve by assessing ovarian volume and follicle counts. It is also a more practical and cost-effective option.²⁴ A study perceived that in Sudanese women, phenotype D is the most common form of PCOS, which is different from the global distribution. Based on our cross-sectional study, we did not find any significant link between levels of vitamin D and AMH or AFC in women who are infertile. This was true even after considering other factors²⁵

CONCLUSION:

The study confirmed that ovarian volume (OV) is larger in fertile patient and smaller in infertile patient.

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